

THE VALUE OF EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING TECHNICAL DISCIPLINES TO STUDENTS

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The article focuses on the importance of extracurricular activities in the assimilation of knowledge gained in English classes for students of technical universities. Extracurricular activities play an important role in the development of the intellectual activity of young people.

In addition to compulsory classes, there are also voluntary forms of teaching a foreign language. Activities aimed at satisfying the creativity and curiosity of students are called "Extracurricular Activities". Extracurricular activities are carried out in different ways depending on the goal. The goal of reforms in the education system in Turkmenistan is to improve the quality of education of young people and develop their creative abilities. Extracurricular activities are a form of student activity that includes upbringing, education and personal development [1].

Purposefully planned extracurricular activities contribute to the inclusion of young people in life, their passion for learning and science, personal development, independence of action and correct behavior in society. Extra-curricular activities are divided into three categories, such as education, entertainment and recreation, and health improvement.

1. Extracurricular activities related to education are aimed at activating the curiosity of students, expanding the range of interests, deepening their knowledge, and forming a civic position of the individual.

2. Recreational extracurricular activities are aimed at developing new skills and competencies that students need in society. Various games and spending time together make student life interesting and strengthen it.

3. Extracurricular activities related to health and physical education ensure the physical development and health of young people. In addition, extra-curricular activities promote healthy competition and foster personal dignity, team cohesion, and respect for the opponent.

Consolidation of technical knowledge of students through extracurricular activities is carried out on the basis of an approved plan. We offer innovative methods of extracurricular activities related to the knowledge gained in the English language classes from students of a technical university, the main area of training, an engineer with a degree in Mechanical Engineering, Mechatronics and Robotics.

According to the plan, the development of special software for solving the problem of designing the design of mechanical modules, control systems and data processing was entrusted to students and the deadlines were set: a) preparation of a presentation of modules in English; b) building an algorithm for modules; (c) organization data management; d) data processing algorithm; e) presentation of sections of the program; f) development of custom software; g) use of a single application.

As we can see, the development of special software is carried out on the basis of a specially developed and approved plan for "Extracurricular activities" with students majoring in "Mechatronics and Robotics".

1. The correct organization of extracurricular activities related to learning activates the student's curiosity, deepens his interest and increases enthusiasm. The student gets the opportunity to apply their theoretical knowledge in practice. The academic competence of a student, which is part of the competences of a future specialist, includes the ability to apply the knowledge and skills acquired in the learning process in practice. The requirements for the academic qualification of students require the ability to work independently and the ability to generate new ideas. The student must know such requirements as possession of analysis skills, an integrated approach to solving problems, knowledge of the latest in scientific and technological development and the ability to implement them in industry [2].

Extracurricular activities serve as a means of facilitating the student's successful fulfillment of the above requirements. To master the theoretical foundations and practical skills of the invention and production of high-tech products, extracurricular activities of students are organized in technoparks, technology centers, and factories.

Extracurricular activities organized in technology centers, factories and technology parks contribute to the complete mastery of production and technological, organizational and managerial, experimental research, research and design activities of students to create high-tech products and equipment. Various extra-curricular activities are organized to teach them how to use their theoretical and practical knowledge in production.

2. Recreational extracurricular activities are aimed at developing new skills and competencies that students need in society. Various games and spending time together make student life interesting and strengthen it. Requirements for the social and personal rights of students, the availability of interpersonal communication skills lead to the adaptation and socialization of students [3].

At the Oguz Han Engineering and Technology University of Turkmenistan, a grant on knowledge of a foreign language called "Language is the key to reason" was announced from February 9 to March 9, 2022. During this month, competitions were held among all teachers and students of the university to determine the level of knowledge of the English language and various events aimed at learning foreign languages.

The competition was aimed at using innovative teaching methods at the university, conducting active, effective and interesting extracurricular activities, improving the speech and thinking skills of students in foreign languages. In order to further improve the level of English language proficiency at a technical university, a number of methodological materials have been prepared within the walls of the university and in educational buildings. Daily news, excerpts from English and Japanese literature were read on the university's radio network. Since our university is specialized in Japanese and English, subjects are taught in these languages.

3. Extra-curricular activities related to health and physical culture are carried out in the form of sports competitions, competitions, excursions and processions that ensure the physical development and health of students. In addition, extra-curricular activities promote healthy competition and foster personal dignity, team cohesion, and respect for the opponent. The student must know the requirements for social and personal competencies, such as the ability to think self-critically, take care of their health, and the ability to work in a team.

The general requirements for obtaining a bachelor's degree state that "a bachelor must be able to constantly and continuously improve his theoretical knowledge and practical skills, properly use in his work the experience and scientific information collected in his field, and organize his activities, work on a scientific basis " [4].

To fulfill this requirement, extra-curricular activities are offered depending on the student's field of study:

– calculation and preparation of projects of individual blocks and structures of mechatronic and robotic complexes that control information-sensor and executive systems according to technical instructions;

– development of special software for solving the problem of designing mechanical and mechatronic modules, control systems and data processing;

– development of a mathematical model for mechatronic and robotic systems, their individual parts, including information, electromechanical, hydraulic, electrohydraulic, electronic structures and computer technology;

– organizes students in technoparks, technology centers, factories to master the theoretical foundations and practical skills in designing and manufacturing high-tech products;

Extracurricular activities are organized in individual, group and collective forms, depending on the number of participants. An individual type of extracurricular work allows us to work with an individual student. The group type of extracurricular work is carried out in groups in accordance with the needs and interests of students. These are events, creative evenings, project competitions, etc.

The content of the collective form of extracurricular activities includes competitive (games, competitions, competitions) events, information and mass events (paintings, exhibitions), cultural events (holiday evenings, excursions) and political events (meetings with people of various professions, creative workers) .

The joint use of individual, group and collective forms of communication contributes to the development of intellectual activity of students.

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